

Magnetic and Spectral Studies of Tris (isonitrosoacetophenonato) Cobalt (III)*

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Magnetic and spectral studies suggest that the orange-red diamagnetic $\text{Co}(\text{INAP})_3$ has a five membered ring structure involving bonding through nitrogen and oxygen atoms.

It is reported that $\text{Co}(\text{II})$ in slightly alkaline medium undergoes oxidation by aerial oxygen in presence of isonitrosoacetophenone (HINAP) to form the orange-red tris(isonitrosoacetophenonato) Cobalt (III), $\text{Co}(\text{INAP})_3$.^{1,2} Taylor and Ewbank¹ suggested that it should be represented by a six-membered ring structure I. Feigl³ proposed that the enolization of

the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group in HINAP and its participation in complex formation should be considered. Patel and Haldar⁴ have concluded from structural studies that tris-(isonitrosoacetylacetonato) Cobalt (III) has a five membered ring structure in which chelate ring is formed by bonding through oxygen and nitrogen donor atoms. Magnetic and spectral properties of $\text{Co}(\text{INAP})_3$ have, therefore, been studied to throw light on its structure.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals and solvents used were of A.R. quality. HINAP was prepared by following the procedure recommended by Welcher⁵. Deuterated isonitrosoacetophenone was obtained by repeated recrystallization of HINAP from 99.9% D_2O and finally drying over P_2O_5 under vacuum. $\text{Co}(\text{INAP})_3$ was prepared by the method reported by Pathak⁶. It was obtained in the form of orange-red crystals by recrystallization from chloroform.

Magnetic susceptibility, NMR, I.R., U.V. and visible spectra were measured with instruments described elsewhere^{4,7}. The assignments of I.R. bands of HINAP were checked by examining the I.R. spectra of deuterated isonitrosoacetophenone.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The orange-red $\text{Co}(\text{INAP})_3$ is insoluble in water and dilute mineral acids but soluble, though to a limited extent, in most organic solvents. It is monomeric and behaves as a non-electrolyte in nitrobenzene solution. Its diamagnetism indicates that it is a spin-paired octahedral complex.

Fig. 1: PMR spectra at 60 Mc/s of (a) isonitrosoacetophenone in dioxane and (b) tris-(isonitrosoacetophenonato) cobalt (III) in CDCl_3 . Chemical shift in ppm relative to tetramethylsilane.

The proton resonance spectrum (Fig. 1a) of HINAP in dioxane solution reveals a very broad peak with maximum around -11.4 due to $=\text{NOH}$ group. Two bands with structures near -8.1 and -7.65 are attributed to proton resonance signals from $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ and $\text{CH} \leftarrow$. The complex $\text{Co}(\text{INAP})_3$ in CDCl_3 exhibits proton signals at -7.25 and -6.77 (Fig. 1b). It does not show proton signal due to the $=\text{NOH}$ indicating that the complexation leads to the replacement of the hydrogen atom of the group $=\text{NOH}$ by cobalt. It may, therefore, be represented by the structure I or II.

II

Co^{59} resonance (Fig. 2) in CDCl_3 solution of the complex occurs towards the high field side from that of tris(acetylacetonato) cobalt (III). Considering the relation deduced by Griffith and Orgel⁸ that the chemical shifts should be linearly related to the reciprocal of the electronic excitation energy produced by the ligand, it is reasonable to conclude that the ligand field due to the anion INAP^- should be greater than that of ethylene diamine. The structure I for $\text{Co}(\text{INAP})_3$ would imply that the field strength due to the anion INAP^- should be close

to that of the acetylacetonate and much less than that of ethylenediamine. The chemical shift of the cobalt resonance seems to support the structure II, which has close resemblance to the structure proposed by Patel and Halder⁴ for tris(isonitrosoacetylacetonato) cobalt (III).

Fig. 2: NMR of ^{69}Co in cobalt complexes. Reference compound tris(acetylacetonato) cobalt (III).

The ultraviolet spectrum of $\text{Co}(\text{INAP})_3$ in methanol solution exhibits a shoulder near 37.37 k μ and a strong peak at 34.36 k μ ($\epsilon = 14,820$) (Fig. 3, I) which are attributed to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in the ligand because the spectrum of the free ligand in methanol solution reveals a strong band at 39.21 k μ ($\epsilon = 10,640$) (Fig. 3, II) and that its solution in 0.1 *N* NaOH shows a shoulder and strong absorption band (Fig. 3, III) at 37.73 and 33.90 k μ ($\epsilon = 5,816$) respectively. The benzene solution of the complex shows the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ band at 33.90 k μ ($\epsilon = 44,310$) (Fig. 3, IV). It also reveals a strong peak and a shoulder at 27.77 k μ ($\epsilon = 28,300$) and 25.00 k μ respectively. The strong peak at 27.77 k μ may also be due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition though the possibility of its origin from charge transfer process is not

Fig. 3: Absorption spectra of isonitrosoacetophenone and tris(isonitrosoacetophenonato) cobalt (III).

- I— $\text{Co}(\text{INAP})_3$ in methanol,
- II—HINAP in methanol,
- III—HINAP in sodium hydroxide solution.
- IV— $\text{Co}(\text{INAP})_3$ in benzene.

excluded. The absorption at 25.00 μ , even after correction for overlap with the tail of the high intensity neighbouring band at 27.77 μ , appears to be too high for a d-d transition band. The shoulder at 25.00 μ may, therefore, be tentatively assigned to a charge transfer band. The d-d transition bands are masked by the presence of high intensity $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and charge transfer bands.

Some important bands observed in the infrared spectra of HINAP and Co(INAP)_3 in the region 4000–400 cm^{-1} and their assignments are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Some important vibrational bands in HINAP and Co(INAP)_3 and their assignments

HINAP (cm^{-1})	Co(INAP)_3 (cm^{-1})	Assignments
3200 (s)	—	Hydrogen-bonded OH stretching
1686 (s)	—	C = O stretching
1600 (s)	1600 (s)	Perturbed C=O and/or C=N stretching
1580 (s)	1500 (s)	Perturbed C=O and/or stretching
1235 (s)	1203 (s)	N—O stretching
—	628 (m)	Co—N vibration.

s = strong; m = medium.

Co(INAP)_3 does not show the band due to hydrogen bonded OH observed in HINAP at 3200 cm^{-1} indicating that the hydrogen atom of the oxime group is replaced by the cobalt atom. This is in agreement with the conclusion arrived at from PMR studies. The peaks at 1600 cm^{-1} and 1500 cm^{-1} in the cobalt complex may be assigned to the perturbed C = O and C = N stretching vibrations. The strong band at 1230 cm^{-1} may be tentatively attributed to N-oxide stretching frequency. This is consistent with the fact that the N-oxide peak⁹ in aromatic ring compounds occurs as a strong band in the region 1300–1200 cm^{-1} . Further, it is reported that tris(dimethylglyoximate) cobalt (III)¹⁰ and tris(isonitrosoacetylacetonato) cobalt (III)⁴ having five-membered ring structures exhibit N-oxide band at 1221 cm^{-1} and 1292 cm^{-1} respectively.

The cobalt complex reveals a band at 628 cm^{-1} which is not observed in the spectrum of the ligand. It may be noted that the bands at 593 cm^{-1} and 587 cm^{-1} in tris(isonitrosoacetylacetonato) cobalt (III) have been assigned to Co-N vibrations⁴. It is reported that the metal-nitrogen stretching vibrations in the chelate compounds of tris-acetylacetonate-ethylenediimine and tris-salicylaldehyde-ethylenediimine occur in the region 580–430 cm^{-1} . Therefore, the assignment of the band at 628 cm^{-1} to Co-N vibration in Co(INAP)_3 appears to be reasonable. It may, however, have a significant contribution from Co-O vibration.

The results of the present investigation support the five-membered chelated ring structure II for Co(INAP)_3 which may also have other resonating forms.

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